

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ICHERISHEHER AND ITCHAN KALA: PRESERVATION OF THE HISTORIC URBAN ENVIRONMENT AND TOURISM POTENTIAL

Gulnar Nazarova¹

¹Azerbaijan Tourism and Management University, PhD Student, Social Management, Social Sciences, Baku, Azerbaijan <https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0000-0002-5870-7397>
Azerbaijan University, Lecturer, Humanities and Social Sciences, Political and Social Sciences, Baku, Azerbaijan

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Abstract. *The presented article conducts a comparative analysis of the historical and architectural complexes of Icherisheher in Azerbaijan and Itchan Kala in Uzbekistan. The purpose of the paper is to identify the architectural and planning features of both historical urban sites, practices applied in the field of cultural heritage preservation, and their role in the development of tourism potential. Comparative-historical, comparative, descriptive and content analysis methods were used during the study. The findings reveal that both complexes are rare examples of the preservation of ancient Eastern urban planning traditions and are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. Fortress walls, palaces, mosques, madrasahs, caravanserais, baths and residential buildings constitute the architectural integrity of these cities. At the same time, there are certain differences in terms of architectural style, building materials, layout and religious and cultural diversity. The results of the research show that both complexes, functioning as Open-Air Museums, play an important role not only in safeguarding national cultural heritage, but also in the development of international tourism and intercultural communication.*

Keywords: *Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan, Icherisheher, Itchan Kala, Cultural heritage, Tourism.*

Introduction

Preservation of the historical urban environment and its transmission to future generations is considered one of the main directions of cultural heritage management in the modern era. City-fortress-type residential areas are among the important historical and cultural sites reflecting the level of social, economic and cultural development of ancient civilizations. In this regard, Icherisheher, which forms the historical core of Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, and Itchan Kala, which is considered the historical center of Khiva, Uzbekistan, are of particular importance. Both complexes are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List and are internationally recognized as rare examples of the preservation of Eastern urban planning traditions. Historical sources show that both Baku and Khiva were important trade centers of the Great Silk Road, and a rich architectural and urban planning heritage was formed as a result of the mutual influence of different cultures. The meeting held on April 27, 2021, between the Icherisheher State Historical and Architectural Reserve Administration and the Itchan Kala

Corresponding Author Gulnar Nazarova ✉ gulnar.nezerova@au.edu.az ✉ Azerbaijan Tourism and Management University, Social Management, Social Sciences, Azerbaijan University, Humanities and Social Sciences, Political and Social Sciences, Baku, Azerbaijan

Reserve Museum of Uzbekistan, during which prospects for cooperation were discussed, further increased the relevance of studying the common features of these two historic sites (Azerbaijan State Information Agency, 2021).

The object of the study is the historical and architectural complexes of Icherisheher and Itchan Kala, and the subject is the significance of these complexes in the world cultural heritage system.

The purpose of the study is to determine their role in the preservation of cultural heritage and the development of tourism by comparative analysis of Icherisheher and Itchan Kala. To achieve the set goal, the following tasks were performed:

- To examine the general characteristics of both city-reserves and their internal structure;
- To identify similarities based on the analysis of the internal structure;
- To systematize the different features existing between the complexes;
- To determine the role of both heritage samples in the field of world culture and tourism based on the results of the comparative analysis.

Method

The research methodology of the article was based on the explanation of historical, cultural and architectural features, therefore, a qualitative approach was adopted. The methods of comparative-historical, comparative analysis, document analysis, descriptive analysis, and content analysis were used during the research:

- ✓ The comparative-historical method was used to compare the historical development stages, formation characteristics, and urban planning traditions of Icherisheher and Itchan Kala;
- ✓ The comparative analysis method was carried out under the criteria based on the identification of similar and different aspects of architectural style, defense systems, cultural and religious heritage samples, tourism potential and conservation policies;
- ✓ Document analysis was used during the analysis of scientific literature, official documents of international organizations, legislative acts, and official reports related to both heritage complexes. The main scientific basis of the study consisted of S. Aşurbəyli's “Bakı şəhərinin tarixi: Orta əsrlər dövrü”, K. İbrahimov's “İçərişəhər.Bakı”, F. Абдухоликов's “Архитектурная эпиграфика Узбекистана: Хива. Ичан қалъа: книга-альбом”, among other sources. These works helped to study the historical and cultural development and architectural features of both complexes. One of the main documents of the source base was the official documents on the UNESCO World Heritage List, on the basis of which the cultural heritage status of the reserves was systematically investigated;
- ✓ The descriptive method was used to describe the architectural elements, urban structure, and historical features of both complexes;
- ✓ Content analysis was used to systematically examine information presented in scientific articles, historical sources, and UNESCO documents.

Figure 2. The Photographs of Icherisheher and Itchan Kala by Amos Chapple

Sources: UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-c); UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-d).

Results or Findings

Similarities and Differences

A comparative analysis of the Icherisheher of Azerbaijan and the Itchan Kala of Uzbekistan was conducted based on scientific sources. As a result of the analysis, similarities and differences in terms of the historical development path, architectural features, urban planning traditions and cultural heritage of both reserves were identified and evaluated.

Similarities

The comparative analysis revealed that both cities share a number of common features. These similarities can be explained by their belonging to Eastern civilization, Islamic culture and urban culture formed on the Great Silk Road.

- ✓ Trade relations: The cities of Baku and Khiva were among the main centers of the Great Silk Road. This factor created the conditions for both cities to have an important strategic position in international trade for centuries. Through trade relations, Baku has established close relations with Uzbekistan, Russia, Dagestan, Circassia, Iran and the countries of the Middle East. Caravanserai in the cities also served as significant stopping points for travelers and merchants (Voyage Uzbekistan, n.d.; Aşurbəyli, 2009);
- ✓ Crafts and traditional industries: In both cities, crafts such as architecture, sculpture, ceramics, jewelry, carpet weaving, coppersmithing, and weapon manufacturing have historically played an important role in cultural life (İbrahimov, 2006; Khabibullaev, 1999, pp. 40-51);
- ✓ Urban structure: Both reserves represent the inner part of the city, known as the shahristan. Khiva, like Baku, consisted of two parts: Itchan Qala (“Inner City”), which was considered the main historical center, and Dishan-Qala (“Outer City”). Itchan Kala included an ark (citadel), shahristan, and rabad sections (Samarkand Tour, n.d.; UNESCO World Heritage Centre, n.d.-b). The historical center of Baku, known as Icherisheher (the Old City, the ancient name of the Baku Fortress), also consisted of the ichgala, shahristan and rabad parts. The population mainly settled in these areas, while artisanal activities were concentrated in the rabad. In the 1840s, Bayir sheher (Outer City) was built as an alternative to the Ichgala. Bayir sheher was larger in terms of area and the houses built there reflected a more modern architectural style (İbrahimov, 2006, p. 12; Musayev, 2006, p. 112);
- ✓ Historical development: Scientific researches indicate that both the Baku Fortress and Itchan Kala are more than two thousand years old (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, n.d.-a; Aşurbəyli, 2009, pp. 44-45);
- ✓ Defensive structure: Both fortresses were historically required to defend themselves. For

this reason, they were surrounded by fortified defensive walls, and merlons and crenels were built on the upper part of the walls. In addition, there were moats filled with water around the fortresses (Samarkand Tour, n.d.; İbrahimov, 2006, pp. 19-20, 99);

- ✓ Functional composition of architectural heritage: Both complexes included various architectural objects such as fortress walls, palaces, mosques, madrasahs, minarets, mausoleums, bazars, baths, and residential houses (İbrahimov, 2006; Samarkand Tour, n.d.);
- ✓ Urban layout system: One of the key similarities between both fortresses is their urban planning structure and principles. These settlements were formed in accordance with the traditions of Eastern urban planning. The street network mainly consisted of narrow streets and dead ends, and creating a labyrinth-like spatial structure (İbrahimov, 2006; Samarkand Tour, n.d.);
- ✓ Decorative architectural features: Tile elements, plant and geometric ornaments were widely used in the decorative design of historical and cultural monuments located on the territory of both complexes. For example, the Shirvanshahs' Mausoleum and the Shirvanshahs' Palace Bath in Icherisheher, and the Muhammad Rakhimkhan II Madrasah and the Pahlavan Mahmud Mausoleum in Itchan Kala are distinguished by their tile decorations. Plant and geometric motifs are observed in the Ashur Mosque and the Khans' Mosque in Icherisheher, as well as in the Pahlavan Mahmud Mausoleum and the Ota Darvoza in Itchan Kala. In addition, Quranic verses and hadith texts were also widely used in the decorative elements of the monuments of both fortresses (İbrahimov, 2006; Абдухоликов et al., 2015);
- ✓ Epigraphic inscriptions: Various types of calligraphic scripts are found in the epigraphic inscriptions on the architectural samples of both reserves. For instance, kufic script was used in the Djuma Mosque in Itchan Kala and the Muhammad Mosque in Icherisheher, while the naskh and nastaliq scripts were used in the Ota Darvoza in Itchan Kala and the Shirvanshahs' Mausoleum in Icherisheher (Aşurbəyli, 2009; Абдухоликов et al., 2015);
- ✓ Use in cinema: Both reserves have managed to preserve their antique appearance and historical and architectural authenticity. This feature has led to their becoming a major object of interest in artistic culture, especially in the film industry. For example, the film "Orlando" was shot in Itchan Kala, while Icherisheher has served as a filming location for movies such as “Arşın mal alan”, “O olmasın, bu olsun”, “Onu bağışlamaq olarmı?”, “Sehrli xalat”, “Şərikli çörək”, “Əli və Nino”, and others (Khabibullaev, 1999, pp. 40-51; Azerhistory, n.d.).

Differences

As a result of the comparative analysis, it was determined that although Icherisheher and Itchan Kala have similar historical and cultural characteristics, they have a number of different aspects in terms of architectural style, construction materials, religious and cultural influences and epigraphic traditions. These differences are associated with the geographical environments in which the two heritage sites developed, their historical evolution, and the characteristics of their respective regional architectural schools. The identified differences are summarized in

Table 1.

Table 1. The Differences Between Icherisheher and Itchan Kala

Criteria	Icherisheher	Itchan Kala
Architectural Style	Shirvan-Absheron architectural school	Central Asian Islamic architecture
Construction Material of the Fortress Walls	Limestone and local stone materials	Baked brick
Height of the Fortress Walls	Approximately 8 m	Approximately 10 m
Layout Plan	Built in an amphitheatrical form	Rectangular layout plan
Area	22 hectares	26 hectares
Gates and Entrance System	Originally had six entrance gates. The Shamakhi (Northern) and Salyan (Southern) gates, constructed in the 12th century, served as the principal entrances. Following the demolition of the second defensive wall in the late 19th century, the Shah Abbas Gate was relocated adjacent to the Shamakhi Gate, forming the well-known Gosha Gala Gates. Additional gates were later opened to facilitate access to the city	Contains four main entrance gates: Ota Darvoza in the west, Bakhcha-Darvaza in the north, Palvan Darwaza in the east, and Tash Darwaza in the south
Religious and Architectural Characteristics	Includes architectural monuments associated with Zoroastrianism, Christianity, and Islam	Predominantly reflects Islamic architectural traditions
Language of Epigraphic Inscriptions	Inscriptions were written mainly in Arabic and Persian	Inscriptions were composed in Arabic, Persian-Tajik, and Old Uzbek languages

Sources: Абдухоликов et al., 2015, pp. 33-326; İbrahimov, 2006, pp. 97-149; UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-a); İbrahimov, 2016, pp. 130-131; Samarkand Tour. (n.d.).

Cultural Heritage Protection Policy

Icherisheher and Itchan Kala began to be protected more systematically from the middle of the 20th century. This policy served both the preservation of cultural heritage and the development of tourism potential. Thus, the architectural and historical monuments located in the territory of both historical cities were protected on the basis of conservation measures and regulatory and legal documents adopted during the USSR.

In 1967, Itchan Kala was declared a State Historical and Architectural Reserve by the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR, and since 1969 it has functioned as a museum-reserve. The Palace of the Shirvanshahs Complex located in Icherisheher has been used as a branch of the Azerbaijan State Museum since 1936, and in 1964 the complex was granted museum status and continued its activities as a State Historical and Architectural Reserve-Museum (UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-a); Ələkbərova, 2018, p. 860). Thus, the

expansion of the museum functions of both reserves has made them more accessible to visitors, has made a significant contribution to the promotion of historical and cultural heritage and the development of tourism activities.

In general, after Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan officially gained independence, new legal and institutional approaches have been formed in the field of cultural heritage protection. In this context, numerous legislative and regulatory legal acts have been adopted to strengthen the protection of historical and architectural monuments of Icherisheher and Itchan Kala. The following are examples of these:

- Icherisheher - Law on the Protection of Historical and Cultural Monuments (1998); Decision No. 132 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated August 2, 2001, on the Approval of the Classification of Immovable Historical and Cultural Monuments under State Protection in the Territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan by Their Significance (2001); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the Approval of the Regulations on the State Historical-Architectural Reserve "Icherisheher" (2005) and etc. (Icherisheher State Historical-Architectural Reserve Administration. (n.d.-a).);
- Itchan Kala - The Law on Architecture and City-building (1995), The Instructions on Rules of Recording, Safeguarding, Maintaining, Utilisation and Restoration of Historical and Cultural Monuments (1986); The Law on Protection and Exploitation of Cultural Heritage Properties (2001) and etc. (UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-a).).

As a result of initiatives undertaken by the governments of Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan, various restoration and conservation projects have been implemented in both reserves. These measures have aimed to preserve the historical and architectural heritage and ensure its transmission to future generations. Examples of these projects are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. *Examples of Restored Historical Monuments in Icherisheher and Itchan Kala*

Icherisheher	Itchan Kala
Gosha Gala Gates	Ota Darvoza, Palvan Darwaza and Tash Darwaza
Juma Mosque	Djuma Mosque
Maiden Tower	Tash-Khawli Palace complex
The Siratagli Religious and Architectural Complex	Complex of Pahlavon Mahmud Mausoleum
Beylar Mosque	Muhammad Rakhimkhan, Shergazikhan, Matniyaz Divan begi, Kutlug Murad inak madrasahs
Underground bath	Palace Complex Kuhna Ark

Sources: İçərişəhər Dövlət Tarix-Memarlıq Qoruğu İdarəsi. (n.d.-b); UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-b).

Tourism Potential

Itchan Kala, which operates as an open-air museum, was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List in 1990, and Icherisheher in 2000. However, in 2003, Icherisheher was placed on UNESCO “List of World Heritage in Danger”, and in 2009, following the successful implementation of large-scale restoration and management measures initiated by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, the site was removed from the list. This process showed the effectiveness of the work carried out to protect and restore the complex. Therefore,

both fortresses have significantly increased the interest of both domestic and international tourists as examples of world cultural heritage (Voyage Uzbekistan. (n.d.); İçərişəhər Dövlət Tarix-Memarlıq Qoruğu İdarəsi. (n.d.-d).).

At present, various souvenir shops, restaurants, hotels, and other tourism-related facilities operate within these historic areas. Furthermore, numerous events are regularly organized in the cities. Events such as festival, dance performance, concert, fair, exhibition, and other cultural activities contribute to increasing tourist arrivals and enhancing the attractiveness of the sites.

In addition, information boards and guidebooks are used to inform the local residents about the protection of the area, as well as to provide visitors with more complete information about the sites. Public awareness-raising work is also conducted through the mass media, master classes, and workshops (İçərişəhər Dövlət Tarix-Memarlıq Qoruğu İdarəsi. (n.d.). İçərişəhər Dövlət Tarix-Memarlıq Qoruğu İdarəsinin rəsmi instagram səhifəsi; UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-b).).

Along with all this, restoration and conservation work on the monuments located inside the fortresses was carried out on the condition of preserving their original physical appearance. Consequently, these monuments have become more attractive and functional from a tourism perspective. Information on selected monuments and their tourism-related functions is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Functional Use of Monuments for Tourism Purposes in Icherisheher and Itchan Kala

Icherisheher		Itchan Kala	
Monument Name	Function	Monument Name	Function
The Palace of the Shirvanshahs	Museum	Muhammad Aminkhan Madrasah	Hotel
Maiden Tower	Museum	Matniyaz Divan begi Madrasah	Restaurant
The Siratagli Religious and Architectural Complex	Open-air museum	Tim and Caravan-Seray of Allakulikhan	Trade center
Beylar Mosque	The Museum of Holy Relics	Kuhna Ark	Summertime cinema
Gasim bey caravanserai	Mugam klub restaurant	Anushakhan bath-houses	Modern bath-houses
Molla Ahmad Mosque	The Museum of Azerbaijani Miniature Art	Muhammad Amin inak Madrasah	House of wedding
Apartment houses on 42 Boyuk Gala Street, 19 Qulla Street	Museum of Archaeology	Kalantar Bobo complex	Tourist bureau
Apartment house on 1, 3rd Ilyas Efendiyev Lane	House-Museum of Tahir Salahov	Atajan bay Madrasah	Workshops of national craftsmen

Sources: İçərişəhər Dövlət Tarix-Memarlıq Qoruğu İdarəsi. (n.d.-c); Nezerova, 2023; Muğam Klub. (n.d.); UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (n.d.-b).

Discussion

The comparative analysis conducted as a result of the article shows that, despite their location in different geographical regions, the historical cities of Icherisheher in Azerbaijan and Itchan Kala in Uzbekistan have common cultural roots and urban planning traditions. Both sites are unique urban examples where Eastern city-planning traditions and Islamic architecture have been preserved. The location of both complexes on the Great Silk Road confirms that they developed not only as regional, but also as international centers of trade and cultural exchange.

The findings indicate that the similarities are more evident at the functional and structural levels. Fortress walls, narrow street networks, mosques, madrasahs, caravanserais, and craft centers formed the basis of the socio-economic life of both cities. Simultaneously, the open-air museum function of the cities also demonstrates that similar strategies are applied in the management of tourism and cultural heritage in the modern era.

However, the differences are primarily associated with regional architectural schools and construction materials. While Icherisheher reflects more Shirvan-Absheron architectural tradition and local stone materials, Itchan Kala demonstrates the aesthetics of Central Asian Islamic architecture formed on baked bricks. These differences can be interpreted as a result of adaptation to local geographical and environmental conditions.

Important parallels are also observed in cultural heritage protection policies. The implementation of conservation measures in both areas since the mid-20th century, and the strengthening of the legal and institutional framework after independence, have ensured their transition toward sustainable management models. UNESCO status, in turn, has enhanced international recognition of these sites and strengthened conservation obligations.

The results further show that tourism activity plays a significant role in the economic and cultural sustainability of these historical cities. Restoration and conservation activities have contributed not only to the preservation of physical heritage, but also to increase tourist flows and the expansion of cultural events.

Conclusion and Implications

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the historical city-reserves of Icherisheher and Itchan Kala confirmed their international cultural significance by being included in the UNESCO World Heritage List as living heritage examples where Eastern urban planning traditions and Islamic architectural heritage are preserved.

Comparative analysis indicates that the similarities are mainly related to the urban structure, functional architectural elements, and historical development trajectories. The differences are explained more by architectural style, building materials and regional cultural influences. This shows that both cities, while maintaining their unique identity, represent a shared Eastern urban culture.

At the same time, state policies, restoration and conservation measures implemented in the field of cultural heritage protection have ensured the sustainability of these sites. The development of the tourism sector has increased their socio-economic value and created an important platform for local communities as well as international intercultural relations.

Overall, the study shows that Icherisheher and Itchan Kala can be considered not only complexes of historical monuments but also cultural heritage centers of strategic importance for preserving cultural memory, maintaining urban identity, and developing global cultural dialogue.

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